

Extensive Perianal Basal Cell Carcinoma: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Basal cell carcinoma is the most common skin cancer. It usually occurs in sun-exposed areas; perianal location is rare. The extension to the anal canal is exceptional, only a few cases were reported in the literature. **Observation:** We report the case of a 58-years-old patient, referred for chronic ulceration of the perianal area. Histopathology revealed an extensive basal cell carcinoma. Wide local excision was performed, with a favourable outcome. **Conclusion:** the main lesson from this case is that although basal cell carcinoma is exceptional in the perianal region, a biopsy is mandatory for all chronic perianal ulcerations.

KEYWORDS Anal canal, basal cell carcinoma, perianal ulceration

Introduction

Perianal basal cell carcinoma is a rare entity, as well as the extension to the anal canal. The diagnosis and the therapeutic management of this condition could be challenging.

Case report:

We report the case of a 58 years old male, unmarried farm worker with low income. The patient had no previous medical history; his primary complaint was an anal lesion evolving for over nine years. The ulceration had a negative impact on both his social and sexual life. No other symptoms were reported by the patient, except intermittent constipation. Different practitioners treated the lesion as anal abscesses, fistulas or fissures. A proctologist referred the patient after performing a biopsy of the lesion. The clinical examination found a 10cmx8cm ulcerovegetative tumour of the anal margin. This lesion extended to the root of the scrotum (Figure 1). The rectal examination revealed the extension of a tumour into the entrance of the anal canal, the testing of the internal and external sphincter tonus found no

Figure 1: Timeline.

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Figure 2: Preoperative view of the lesion, notice the macroscopic infiltration of the anal orifice.

continence problems. The rest of the physical examination was normal. Rectoscopy with staged biopsies was performed, the macroscopic appearance was normal, histology revealed a simple inflammatory reaction without tumour cells in the anal canal. Given the size and the long evolution of the lesion, an extensive workup was carried out (a thoraco abdominopelvic CT scan); no distant metastases or significant locoregional lymph nodes were found.

A defunctioning colostomy was initially performed, immediately followed by a wide tumour excision. A margin of 1 cm was observed in the perineum, the resection continued in the anal canal up to the pectinate line, taking away the external sphincter. The internal sphincter looked intact, and it was preserved. Additional biopsies were made higher in the anal canal. The pathology report of the surgical specimen confirms the diagnosis of an infiltrating and moderately differentiated ulceronodular basal cell carcinoma. The lateral margins were a tumour free; the tumor infiltrated the external sphincter, the internal sphincter was healthy. A week later, the perineal wound was covered by a thin skin graft. The wound healed three weeks later. Two months after the operation, the patient presented with incomplete anal stenosis, which required three sessions of dilatation leading to the favourable outcome. The patient was regularly seen for check-ups, he resumed his previous activities right after the last anal dilatation. No recurrence was seen four years after surgery (Figure 1).

DISCUSSION

BCC is the most common cutaneous carcinomas [1]. They occur most often in elderly subjects, but it is more and more common among subjects in a second or third decade. Although BCC is often seen in exposed areas, the most frequent sites of incidence are not those of maximum solar exposure [2]. It is assumed that in addition to the effects of UV, there is an involvement of the embryological closure zones [3]. The perianal occurrence of basal cell carcinomas is less than 0.5% and excluding patients with genodermatoses (Gorlin syndrome type or xeroderma pigmentosum), this frequency is close to 0.27% in the last major published series [4]. The perianal occurrence is rare, the exten-

sion to the anal canal is Exceptional [5]. Clinical examination often leads to the diagnosis of basal cell carcinoma characterised by a pearly, rounded, translucent and telangiectatic lesion that spreads progressively [6]. However, in the perianal region, the diagnosis can be delayed from a few months to many years (embarrassed patients tend to delay first medical consultation). The tumor then is typically an ulcerous lesion, bordered by a peripheral rim; At this stage it is unlikely to be confused with an abscess or a fissure; A biopsy is often needed to eliminate more frequent and sometimes more serious tumors: squamous cell carcinomas and verrucous carcinomas that are responsible for almost three quarters of perianal tumors [7]. Melanoma, Paget's disease and Bowen's disease should also be differentiated. Cloacogenic carcinoma (basaloid carcinoma) should be eliminated. This carcinoma is locally aggressive; it can also metastasise, and therefore requires a more radical treatment [4]. Sometimes, only the immunohistochemistry confirms the diagnosis of basal cell carcinoma.

Treatment is primarily based on surgery. The resection of a tumour with a safety margin of 10 mm is often sufficient [7]. Radical surgery, such as abdominoperineal resection, is rarely needed. Some authors propose neoadjuvant external radiotherapy for locally advanced tumours [8]. For others, it is an alternative to surgery in case of surgical contraindications, or if the patient refuses a mutilating intervention. Chemotherapy does not yet have a place in the therapeutic arsenal of basal cell carcinoma. Nevertheless, Imiquimod in topical treatment seems to give promising results for superficial BCC [9]. Fluorouracil cream is being evaluated for the same purpose.

Basal cell carcinoma is generally of good prognosis. It is locally invasive and rarely metastasises: a single case with lymph node metastasis has been reported in the literature [8]. Recurrence after local excision is very rare: none in the series of Pateron and Al and only one case in Gibson's [4; 10]. Even though the diagnosis is often late, and the treatment is more aggressive is the perianal location, the prognosis is still reasonable compared to other histological entities.

CONCLUSION

The perianal location of BCC is exceptional. In advanced stages, only the histology establishes the diagnosis with certainty. Extension to the anal canal is the result of late diagnosis and management.

The takeaway lesson of this case is to highlight the necessity to educate practitioners on the value of performing biopsies over chronic or recurrent lesions of the perianal region.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Verola, Olivier. les tumeurs épithéliales cutanées. Rappels anatomo-pathologiques. *Ann Chir Plast esthét*, 1998,43, N°, 301-310.
2. Guichard , Stéphane. Chirurgie des tumeurs cutanées . Techniques chirurgicales - Chirurgie plastique reconstructrice et esthétique [45-140], 1999.

3. Panje WR, Ceilly RI. The influence of embryology of the mid face in the spread of epithelial malignancies. *Laryngoscope* 1979; 89 : 1914-1920
4. Gibson GE, Ahmed I. Perianal and genital basal cell carcinoma: A clinicopathologic review of 51 cases. *J Am Acad Dermatology* 2001; 45: 68-71.
5. A.C. Simo, N. Jarjous, A. P. Jam, A. Pauwels Carcinome basocellulaire périanal étendu au canal anal . *Gastroentérologie Clinique et Biologique* .Vol 32 - N° 3 .P. 337-338 - mars 2008
6. B. Pinatel, A. Mojallal. Prise en charge diagnostique et thérapeutique du carcinome cutané basocellulaire – Analyse des recommandations .*Annales de Chirurgie Plastique Esthétique*, Volume 57, Issue 2, April 2012, Pages 92-105.
7. Augey F, Cognat T, Balme B, Thomas L, Moulin G. Le carcinome basocellulaire périanal. À propos de 2 cas. *Ann Dermatol Venereol* 1994; 121: 476-8.
8. Nielsen OV, Jensen SL. Basal cell carcinoma of the anus. A clinical study of 34 cases. *Br J Surg* 1981; 68:856-7.
9. Bukhardt Perez MP, Ruiz-Villaverde R, Naranjo Diaz MJ, Blasco MJ, Naranjo SR. Basal cell carcinoma: treatment with imiquimod. *Int J Dermatol* 2007;46:539—42.
10. Paterson CA, Young-Fadok TM, Dozois RR. Basal cell carcinoma of the perianal region: 20-year experience. *Dis Colon Rectum* 1999;42:1200—2.